

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842
ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue I, January 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678 / Business Permit No. 8183

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WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024)/ International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

CHALLENGES IN THE UTILIZATION OF MAKESHIFT CLASSROOMS IN DELA PAZ ELEMENTARY SCHOOL: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

This research titled "Challenges in the Utilization of Makeshift Classrooms in Dela Paz Elementary School: A Phenomenological Research" was conducted during the School Year 2022-2023. Its objective is to identify the challenges faced by students and teachers in makeshift classrooms, and to propose potential solutions to address these challenges. The specific qualitative research approach chosen for this study was the phenomenology model. Phenomenological research, as a qualitative approach, aims to comprehend and describe the universal essence of a phenomenon. This method investigates the everyday experiences of human beings while suspending researchers' preconceived assumptions about the phenomenon. To determine the participants, a systematic sampling method was used to select one (1) section representative in eight (8) sections and two (2) representatives in the pilot section, ensuring that all shifts were adequately represented. As for teacher participants, eight (8) Grade 5 teacher advisers were invited to answer the questions in one-on-one interviews. The interview methodology was employed to gather data for the research. As a data-gathering technique, a semi-structured interview method was designed to obtain the needed information for the study. Researchers formulated open-ended questions for participants to answer. To ensure clarity on the topic, participants were prompted to explain the stated challenges through clarifying and follow-up questions. For a better understanding of the collected data, researchers re-examined the information and asked participants to clarify statements made during the interview. Participants shared their experiences in an open-ended style, allowing the researcher to practice effective listening and provide clarifying questions if a notion was unclear. Students and teachers in makeshift classrooms face various challenges, including physical, safety, security, cost-related, lesson presentation, and assessment challenges. Physical challenges involve inadequate surroundings, ventilation, and space. Safety concerns include health issues like coughing and dizziness, as well as accidents. Students incur costs for classroom maintenance, while teachers contribute to makeshift classroom construction. Lesson presentation challenges include difficulty hearing instructions and limited visibility of board writings. Both students and teachers encounter challenges in conducting class activities, such as limited time, space, facilities, heat, and noise. During assessments, students struggle to focus due to noise, and teachers face difficulties obtaining valid results due to space, time constraints, noise, and disruptions.

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Keywords: makeshift classrooms, physical challenges, safety challenges, cost incurred, lesson presentation, activities, and assessment challenges.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10538063

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